

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

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UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Cauchy Problem for a Nonstationary Third-Order Composite Type Equation on a Plane

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Abstract

This work provides a method for constructing a solution to the Cauchy problem for a non-stationary third-order composite equation in space (x, y, t) . The authors determine the largest uniqueness class depending on the asymptotic properties of the fundamental solutions.

Keywords: the Cauchy problem, the Airy function, variation, functions with bounded variation, existence.

1. Introduction

The aim of this work is to study some properties of solutions of the equation

$$u_{xxx} + u_{yyy} - u_t = 0, \quad (1)$$

in the domain

$$D = \{(x, y, t) : -\infty < x < \infty, -\infty < y < \infty, 0 < t \leq T\},$$

with the initial condition

$$u(x, y, 0) = u_0(x, y), \quad -\infty < x < \infty, -\infty < y < \infty. \quad (2)$$

Reference [2] established a foundational framework for the equation

$$u_{xxx} - u_y = 0, \quad (\text{MC})$$

including the construction of a fundamental solution, the development of potential theory, and a methodology for addressing boundary value and Cauchy problems.

Building upon this, work [3] extended the analysis by deriving a solution of the Cauchy problem within a broader class and investigating its properties. Following this approach, [4] applied the same method to solve the Cauchy problem for a higher-order odd equation.

$$\frac{\partial^{2n+1} u}{\partial x^{2n+1}} + (-1)^n \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = 0.$$

The solutions of equation

$$u_{xxx} + u_{yyy} - u_t = 0 \quad (1)$$

and the linear Zakharov–Kuznetsov equation (equations, as referenced in [6–7])

$$u_{xxx} + u_{yyy} + u_t = 0 \quad (3)$$

exhibit similar asymptotic behavior at infinity.

As a multidimensional generalization of the Korteweg–de Vries equation, the Zakharov–Kuznetsov equation (3) describes ion–acoustic wave propagation in plasma [7].

A. N. Tikhonov [15] introduced correctness classes for the Cauchy problem in growing function spaces using the heat equation. Later, generalized functions [9–11] aided in studying initial–boundary value problems for even–order equations. The theory of linear even–order equations, especially parabolic ones, is now well developed [5,12–13].

A fundamental solution for equation (1) within the space \mathbb{R}^{n+1} was constructed in [1].

Statement of the problem

It is required to determine, in the domain

$$D = \{(x, y, t) : -\infty < x < \infty, -\infty < y < \infty, 0 < t \leq T\},$$

a function $u(x, y, t)$ that has a regular solution of the following equation:

$$u_{xxx} + u_{yyy} - u_t = 0. \quad (1)$$

The function $u(x, y, t)$ is required to satisfy the following condition in the domain D :

$$u(x, y, 0) = u_0(x, y), \quad -\infty < x < \infty, -\infty < y < \infty. \quad (2)$$

Here $u_0(x, y)$ is a given function.

The following function is a fundamental solution of equation (1) [1].

$$U(x, y; \xi, \eta) = (t - \tau)^{-\frac{2}{3}} f\left(\frac{x - \xi}{(t - \tau)^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right) f\left(\frac{y - \eta}{(t - \tau)^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right), \quad x \neq \xi, y \neq \eta, t > \tau. \quad (4)$$

where

$$f(t) = \int_0^{+\infty} \cos(\lambda^3 - \lambda t) d\lambda, \quad -\infty < t < +\infty, \quad (1)$$

called Airy functions, satisfy the following equation [2]:

$$z''(\xi) + \frac{1}{3} \xi z(\xi) = 0. \quad (5)$$

The following relations hold:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} f(t) dt = \frac{2\pi}{3}, \quad \int_{-\infty}^0 f(t) dt = \frac{\pi}{3}. \quad (6)$$

Moreover, for $t \neq 0$ the following equality is valid:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} U(x, y, t) dx dy = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) d\xi \cdot \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\tau) d\tau = \pi^2. \quad (7)$$

Theorem 1. Let $u_0(x, y)$ be a continuous function of bounded variation on a bounded domain

$$D = \{(x, y) : a \leq x \leq b, a \leq y \leq b\} \subset \mathbb{R}^2,$$

and let u_0 have bounded variation in D . Then the function

$$u(x, y, t) = \frac{1}{\pi^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2} U(x - \xi, y - \eta, t) u_0(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta \quad (8)$$

for $t > 0$ satisfies equation (1), and for any $(x_0, y_0) \in D$ the following limit relation holds:

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0^+} u(x, y, t) = \frac{2}{3} u_0(x_0 - 0, y_0 - 0) + \frac{1}{3} u_0(x_0 + 0, y_0 + 0). \quad (9)$$

The validity of the first part of the theorem follows immediately from the properties of the fundamental solution of equation (1) and the assumptions of the theorem. The proof of the second part is carried out separately with respect to each spatial variable. Since this proof is similar to that presented in [3] and does not involve any essential difficulties, it is omitted.

Theorem 2. Let the function $u_0(x, y)$, defined on any bounded domain

$$D_{(a_j, b_j)} = \{(x, y) : a_j \leq x \leq b_j, a_j \leq y \leq b_j\}, \quad j = 1, 2,$$

where $D_{(a_j, b_j)} \subset \mathbb{R}^2$, be continuous and have bounded variation. Assume also that the variation of the function

$$|z|^{\frac{3}{4} + \delta_1} \psi(z)$$

is bounded for any $z < a_0$, where $a_0 = \text{const}$.

Moreover, let the following asymptotic estimates hold:

$$u_0(x, y) \sim O\left(\exp\{\text{const}(|x|^{\frac{3}{2}} + |y|^{\frac{3}{2}})\}\right), \quad x \rightarrow \infty, y \rightarrow \infty, \quad (2)$$

$$u_0(x, y) \sim O\left(\psi(y) \exp\{\text{const}|x|^{\frac{3}{2}}\}\right), \quad x \rightarrow \infty, y < a, \quad (3)$$

$$u_0(x, y) \sim O\left(\psi(x) \exp\{\text{const}|y|^{\frac{3}{2}}\}\right), \quad x < a, y \rightarrow \infty, \quad (4)$$

$$u_0(x, y) \sim O(\psi(x)\psi(y)), \quad x < a, y < a, \quad (5)$$

where δ_1, δ_2 are sufficiently small positive numbers.

Therefore, for $t > 0$, the formula

$$u(x, y, t) = \frac{1}{\pi^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2} U(x - \xi, y - \eta, t) u_0(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta \quad (10)$$

provides a solution of equation (1) and satisfies the condition

$$\lim_{(x, y, t) \rightarrow (x_0, y_0, 0^+)} u(x, y, t) = u_0(x_0, y_0). \quad (11)$$

Proof. We prove the first part of the theorem. To this end, we formally differentiate expression (10) with respect to the variables x and y , which yields

$$u_{xx}(x, y, t) + u_{yy}(x, y, t) =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left[U_{xx}(x - \xi, y - \eta, t) + U_{yy}(x - \xi, y - \eta, t) \right] u_0(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta = \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \left[U_{xx}(x, y, t) + U_{yy}(x, y, t) \right] u_0(x - \xi, y - \eta) d\xi d\eta.
\end{aligned}$$

Using relation (5) in the calculation of the derivatives, we find

$$\begin{aligned}
\pi^2 t (u_{xx} + u_{yy}) &= -\frac{1}{3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) f(\eta) u_0 \left(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}} \right) d\xi d\eta \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\eta) d\eta \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi f'(\xi) u_0 \left(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}} \right) d\xi \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{3} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\xi) d\xi \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \eta f'(\eta) u_0 \left(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}} \right) d\eta \\
&= -\frac{1}{3} \{ u_1(x, y) + u_2(x, y) + u_3(x, y) \}.
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

We will show that if the conditions of Theorem 2 are satisfied, then the formally differentiated integral in (12) converges uniformly.

The following relations are valid for the Airy functions [3]:

$$\begin{aligned}
f(z) &\sim z^{-\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(-\frac{2}{3}|z|^{\frac{3}{2}}\right) \left(\sqrt{\pi} + O\left(|z|^{-\frac{3}{2}}\right)\right), \\
f'(z) &\sim z^{\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(-\frac{2}{3}|z|^{\frac{3}{2}}\right) \left(\sqrt{\pi} + O\left(|z|^{-\frac{3}{2}}\right)\right),
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

For sufficiently large negative z , the following asymptotic relations hold:

$$\begin{aligned}
f(z) &\sim z^{-\frac{1}{4}} \cos\left(\frac{2}{3}|z|^{\frac{3}{2}} - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \left(\sqrt{\pi} + O\left(|z|^{-\frac{3}{2}}\right)\right), \\
f'(z) &\sim z^{\frac{1}{4}} \sin\left(\frac{2}{3}|z|^{\frac{3}{2}} - \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \left(\sqrt{\pi} + O\left(|z|^{-\frac{3}{2}}\right)\right),
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

for sufficiently large positive z .

First, we examine the second term on the right-hand side of (12). The third term is treated similarly.

From (12), for sufficiently large positive numbers r and s , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
u_2(x, y, t) &= \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\eta) d\eta \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \xi f'(\xi) u_0 \left(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}} \right) d\xi = \\
&= \left(\int_{-\infty}^{-r} + \int_{-r}^r + \int_r^{+\infty} \right) f(\eta) d\eta \left(\int_{-\infty}^{-s} + \int_{-s}^s + \int_s^{+\infty} \right) \xi f'(\xi) u_0 \left(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}} \right) d\xi = \\
&= \left(\int_{-\infty}^{-r} + \int_{-r}^r + \int_r^{+\infty} \right) f(\eta) d\eta \left(\int_{-\infty}^{-s} + \int_{-s}^s + \int_s^{+\infty} \right) (J_1, J_2, J_3) d\xi.
\end{aligned}$$

Let $\xi \in (-\infty, -s]$ and $\eta \in (-\infty, -r]$. Then, by virtue of condition (13), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J_1(x, y, t) &= \int_{-\infty}^{-r} f(\eta) d\eta \int_{-\infty}^{-s} \xi f'(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}) u_0(x - \xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}, y - \eta t^{\frac{1}{3}}) d\xi \\ &\sim O\left(\int_r^{+\infty} \eta^{-\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(-\eta^{\frac{3}{2}} \left[\frac{2}{3} - Cy^{-\delta_2} \left(\frac{y}{\eta t^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}-\delta_2}\right]\right) d\eta\right) \\ &\quad \times O\left(\int_s^{+\infty} \xi^{-\frac{1}{4}} \exp\left(-\xi^{\frac{3}{2}} \left[\frac{2}{3} - Cy^{-\delta_1} \left(\frac{y}{\xi t^{\frac{1}{3}}}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}-\delta_1}\right]\right) d\xi\right). \end{aligned}$$

This integral converges uniformly to zero as $s \rightarrow \infty$ and $r \rightarrow \infty$.

Similarly, it can be shown that in the cases $\xi \in (-\infty, -s]$, $\eta \in [r, +\infty)$ and $\xi \in [s, +\infty)$, $\eta \in (-\infty, -r]$ the corresponding integrals also converge uniformly.

Let $\xi \in [s, +\infty)$ and $\eta \in [r, +\infty)$. The convergence of the integrals J_1 and J_2 follows from [16].

Following a similar approach for the remaining integral, we obtain uniform convergence of the integrals for $t > t_0 > 0$ and $a \leq x \leq b$. Consequently, differentiation under the integral sign is justified. Using functions with compact support, it is proved that representation (10) satisfies relation (11).

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